

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF FREE EDGE STRESSES IN SCALED GLASS FIBRE/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH CURVATURE

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ABSTRACT: The size effects are obtaining recently more attention as seen by the number of papers addressing the topic. However, the little attention has been given so far to the size effect in free edge induced failures. This situation gave motivation to investigations of the size effect in composite laminates with failure dominated by highly localised effects caused by the free edge.

This paper presents the results of the numerical investigations of the size effect in curved glass fibre/epoxy composite laminates loaded in bending. The finite element models of the curved sections of the scaled laminates have been developed and analysed. The following stacking sequence was realised $(0_2/\pm 45_3)_S$, $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$ and $(0_8/\pm 45_{12})_S$, resulting in 16-ply, 32-ply and 64-ply laminates respectively.

The Weibull distribution was applied to describe the relations of interlaminar normal and shear stresses for series of scaled specimens. The results of the investigations show the evidence of the size effects in curved glass fibre/epoxy composite laminates loaded in bending. The weakest link theory and its widely used Weibull distribution function have been successfully applied to analyse the results of numerical analysis of the scaled specimens. The results show the evidence of size effects in curved composite laminates with failure controlled by free edge delamination.

KEYWORDS: Composite laminates, free edge, size effect, Weibull distribution, finite elements.

INTRODUCTION

The size effects are very important from practical reasons since the design of large composite structure bases on the material strength characteristics that are usually performed on relatively small samples. If ignored, the size effects could lead to disastrous failures. Therefore, there is a need for better understanding of the effect of specimen size on its strength in order to develop more efficient and reliable composite structures. The strength, with no exception for the through thickness tensile strength, is a material property sensitive to process induced structural imperfections, as reported by many authors, especially Zweben [1] and Wisnom [2]. This implies the existence of size effects, since the probability of defects is higher in larger specimen than in smaller ones.

The application of curved specimen loaded in bending for measuring the through thickness strength is rather a straightforward procedure for unidirectional composite laminates. The issue becomes more complicated when tests are performed on the laminates with stacking sequence promoting the free edge failure. Kaczmarek, Wisnom and Jones [3] studied the delamination of curved specimens with the $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$ lay-up caused by highly localised free edge effects. The study showed that failure was dominated by the free edge induced interlaminar tensile stresses. The issue of size effect on through thickness tensile strength of unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy composites was studied and reported by Wisnom and Jones [4].

The experimental investigations of composite laminates with failure dominated by highly localised stresses at the free edge show the evidence for size effect [5], which usually is associated rather with the volume effects. The results of experimental investigations presented there are complemented by the numerical analyses reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Three sets of specimen differing in size were designed for the analysis of the size effect. The dimensions of the specimens were the same as used by Wisnom and Jones [4] for studying the size effects in interlaminar tensile strength in unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy curved laminates. The dimensions of the smallest (C series) and largest (F series) specimens are obtained by dividing and multiplying, respectively, all the dimensions of the middle specimen by a factor of 2. Static four-point bending tests were carried out on 16-ply, 32-ply and 64-ply curved beam specimens with all the dimensions scaled, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Computer models of the curved beam specimens applied for size effect analysis.

Since the laminates were made by laying-up the layers of 0,125mm thick pre-preg, the specimen stacking sequence was also scaled to enable comparison. The following stacking sequence was realised $(0_2/\pm 45_3)_S$, $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$ and $(0_8/\pm 45_{12})_S$, resulting in 16-ply, 32-ply and 64-ply laminates respectively. The nominal dimensions of specimens are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Nominal dimensions of scaled specimens.

No. of plies	Lay-up	In. radius	Thickness	Width	Short span	Long span	Test rate
		r [mm]	t [mm]	w [mm]	l [mm]	L [mm]	[mm/sec]
16	$(0_2/\pm 45_3)_S$	4	2	5	30	60	0,015
32	$(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$	8	4	10	60	120	0,03
64	$(0_8/\pm 45_{12})_S$	16	8	20	120	240	0,06

Hexcel Composites [6] Fibredux 913G-E-5-30 pre-preg was laid up by hand over a steel tool. Vacuum consolidation was applied after every two-to-four plies to reduce amount of air voids in the specimens. Three separate panels, one per specimen dimension, were produced. The commercial autoclave was used for curing the panels of the stacked pre-preg. Temperature and pressure was controlled during the autoclave process. In the first minute of the process the vacuum bag was pressurised and the overpressure of 0,7MPa was introduced in the autoclave and kept constant throughout the whole process. The temperature regime was programmed in the autoclave and it was controlled by four thermocouples mounted to the steel tool. The temperature rise of 2K per minute was realised. The dwells were applied in order to equalise the temperature in the stack:

- 16-ply - no dwell,
- 32-ply - dwell of 75 minutes at 90°C,
- 64-ply - dwell of 180 minutes at 90°C.

The curing at temperature of 120°C was realised over 60 min for all specimen types. Afterwards the stack was cooled down with the autoclave (approx. 0,6K per minute). Specimens were cut from cured panel using a diamond wheel. The edges of the specimens were polished.

Tests were carried out on the Schenck PSB 100 test machine operating under displacement control with a test rate of 0,015 mm/sec, 0,03 mm/sec and 0,06 mm/sec for 16-ply, 32-ply and 64-ply respectively. The specimens were mounted in a specially prepared rig with adjustable positions of supports to account for scaled values of short and long span. The support ends were made round with the diameter of 5, 10 and 20 mm for the 16-, 32-, and 64-ply specimens, respectively. The contact of the specimen with the supports was indirect. Thin Teflon film was placed in-between to reduce the friction and minimise the restraint on the specimen deformations. All specimens were fitted with strain gauges on both inner and outer radii at the centre of the curved section, as shown in Figure 2. The size of strain gauges was 1mm x 1mm. The load, crosshead displacement and the strain gauge reading were recorded during the course of each test.

Figure 2. Schematic of the specimen equipped with strain gages.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

All specimens failed suddenly, with no prior damage visible. Most of the specimens failed by delamination at the uppermost interface between block of 0 plies and ± 45 plies. The delamination occurred according to the Mode I of fracture mechanics and was caused by the free edge effect that results in high through thickness tensile stresses localised at the free edge. The results are consistent with the previously reported for similar specimens by Kaczmarek, Wisnom and Jones [3] and later Kaczmarek [5].

The values of measured moment per unit width and readings from strain gauges are presented in Table 2. The moment per unit width values were derived based on the force at failure recorded during the experiment. The real specimen dimensions were different than nominal. The width in majority of the specimens is smaller than nominal. This is a result of cutting and polishing processes. Similarly, the thickness of the specimens differs from the nominal values. The smallest specimens actually are thinner than desired due to relatively large amounts of resin out-flowing to the edges of the panels during cure. The amount of out-flowing resin for two large panels was relatively smaller and therefore the thickness of the large panels is higher than the nominal values. The correction of measured strains and load at failure was applied to account for variations of specimen thickness and width as compared with nominal values.

Figure 3. Free edge induced delamination in scaled specimens.

Table 2: Selected experimental results at failure for the scaled specimen.

Specimen series	Lay-up	M	ϵ_b	ϵ_t
		[Nmm/mm]	[%]	[%]
C	$(0_2/\pm 45_3)_S$	403,41	2,17	1,73
D	$(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$	1488,65	1,96	1,61
F	$(0_8/\pm 45_{12})_S$	4019,00	1,34	1,09

As a result of large displacement and friction of the specimens with the supporting rollers there was a significant axial strain present that superimposes with strains caused by pure bending. The situation was complicated by the three dimensional effects. Due to this fact the determination of bending moment at failure would be inaccurate. Therefore, the strain gauge readings as well as the measured load at failure were corrected to account also for those effects. This was done by correcting the measured strains for axial strain, based on the expected ratio of surface strains for pure bending. The ratio of the surface strains for pure bending has been obtained from the 3-D numerical simulations. Kaczmarek presented same correction approach elsewhere [5].

NUMERICAL MODEL

Modelling of the whole specimen would result in a very large model, which for the large specimen (64-ply) would account for over 1 million finite elements. The required computational power and time would make such analysis impractical. Therefore, only part of the whole specimen was modelled numerically as presented in Figure 4. Due to natural symmetry only half width was modelled. The model was created in the cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) and for all types of specimen (16-, 32- and 64-ply) was prepared in the same way. Numerical models were created and the solutions were derived commercial software tool in ABAQUS [7]. Such model required application of appropriate boundary conditions, which made the model deformation equal to that of the whole specimen. The boundary conditions are schematically presented in Figure 5. All nodes in the ABDC plane were fixed in the direction normal to the plane. The BDHF plane was the plane of symmetry. The loading was applied to the model in a form of two pairs of forces: first in nodes E and G, second in nodes F

and H. Their values were calculated based on the corrected bending moment at failure obtained in the experiments. All nodes in the EG line were restraint by means of the *KINEMATIC COUPLING function [7], to have identical value of movement in the θ direction.

Figure 4. Schematic of the part of specimen modelled in ABAQUS [7].

Figure 5: Boundary conditions, loading and cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ , z).

Each ply was modelled separately as an orthotropic laminate layer and appropriate material orientation was applied to obtain required lay-up. The elastic properties of unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy orthotropic lamina are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Elastic properties of unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy orthotropic lamina [3].

$E_r = 15,4\text{GPa}$	$G_{\theta z} = 4,34\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{\theta z} = 0,30$	$\alpha_r = 30,0 \times 10^{-6}$
$E_\theta = 43,9\text{GPa}$	$G_{rz} = 5,31\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{rz} = 0,45$	$\alpha_\theta = 6,6 \times 10^{-6}$
$E_z = 15,4\text{GPa}$	$G_{r\theta} = 4,34\text{GPa}$	$\nu_{r\theta} = 0,105$	$\alpha_z = 30,0 \times 10^{-6}$

Figure 6. Orientation of material coordinate system for 0, -45 and +45 plies.

20-noded solid finite elements (C3D20R) were used. These are isoparametric elements with reduced integration. Meshing was realised in a way that the element size was scaled with scaling the specimens. The exception was the r axis, where the element thickness was the same for all specimen types, because the lamina thickness was in all cases the same: equal to pre-preg thickness of 0,125mm. In case of largest specimen type (series F), two elements per lamina thickness were applied only in a region around the uppermost 0/45 interface, four plies either way. Mesh along the θ axis was non-uniform. The element size was smaller at the analysed cross-section of the specimen (r-z plane) and it was gradually bigger while going away from that plane along the θ axis. In each element the ratio of the shortest side to the longest side was checked. Higher ratios would negatively impact the

numerical convergence and quality of the results. Obtained mesh is a result of number of meshing iterations performed with the goal to prepare the mesh fine enough to cover the areas of high stress gradients (free edge). On the other hand too fine mesh would result in a large number of elements and nodes, hence long required calculation times. Finite element meshes for all three specimen types are presented in Figure 7. Comparison of the selected parameters of the finite element models is given in Table 4.

Figure 7. Finite element meshes shown on a part of the finite element model.

Table 4: Selected parameters of the finite element models of scaled specimen.

Specimen type	No. of elements	No. of nodes	Element size along given axis		
			r [mm]	θ [mm]	z [mm]
C	13 312	58 971	0,0625	0,0694	0,0618
D	32 768	142 049	0,0625	0,1729	0,1292
F	29 952	131 011	0,0625	0,3459	0,2865

The iterative solver was utilised. The numerical calculations were performed with the application of the Silicon Graphics Origin 2000 server, equipped with two R10000 / 250MHz processors, 1024MB RAM each. The calculation time for the model of the middle specimen (D series) was around 4 hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The free edge effect is expressed by the presence of interlaminar stress components at the free edge. Therefore, only the interlaminar stress components are presented in this paper. Interlaminar stress distributions at failure load (σ_{zz} , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} respectively) in the curved section of the 16-, 32-, and 64-ply specimen (C, D and F series) are presented in Figures 8, 9 and 10, respectively. The calculated values of the maximum interlaminar stress at failure load are given in Table 5.

High interlaminar stresses develop at ply interfaces in the free edge region. The width of that free edge region is approximately half of the specimen thickness for all specimen types. The interlaminar stresses in all specimen types are of similar distributions, however the different number of ± 45 interfaces results in a different number of stress “fringe” patterns visible in the stress distributions. This effect is especially evident in the interlaminar shear stress distribution. The interlaminar stresses that develop in the free edge boundary region are localised in the ± 45 plies below the uppermost 0/45 ply interface. That localisation is caused by the curvature and bending loading of the specimens. In a flat laminate the interlaminar stress distributions would be symmetrical as presented by Kaczmarek [8, 9]. The uppermost 0/45 ply interface is the interface, where delamination occurs as observed during the experiments and explained by application of the improved fracture mechanics approach [3, 8]. The main cause for delamination is the high interlaminar tensile stresses that act on the uppermost 0/45 ply interface.

Figure 8. Interlaminar stress distributions at failure (σ_{zz} , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} respectively) in the curved section of the 16-ply specimen (C series).

Figure 9. Interlaminar stress distributions at failure (σ_{zz} , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} respectively) in the curved section of the 32-ply specimen (D series).

Figure 10. Interlaminar stress distributions at failure (σ_{zz} , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} respectively) in the curved section of the 64-ply specimen (F series).

Table 5: Maximum values of interlaminar tensile and shear stresses at failure for scaled specimen.

Specimen type (series)	Lay-up	σ_{zz}	τ_{xz}	τ_{yz}
		[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]
C	$(0_2/\pm 45_3)_S$	102,7	69,5	75,0
D	$(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$	95,6	57,5	61,5
F	$(0_8/\pm 45_{12})_S$	71,9	35,7	38,1

If the strength distribution of a material is described by Weibull theory [10] it is possible to correlate the strengths of specimens of various size. For two specimens of volumes V_1 and V_2 subject to identical stress distributions σ_1 and σ_2 the magnitude of the size effect can be determined by Equation (1) by assuming equal survival probabilities:

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \quad (1)$$

This equation directly links strength to volume and hence quantifies the size effect. The value of Weibull modulus m can be deduced by plotting strengths against volumes in ln-ln scale.

The calculated maximum values of interlaminar tensile and shear stresses for all scaled specimen types were used to determine the size effect by application of the Weibull theory and the Equation (1). In order to perform the analysis the assumption was made that the distributions of the interlaminar tensile and shear stresses are identical in all specimen types. The stressed volume was calculated by the following formula:

$$V = \frac{\pi}{2} (r_o^2 - r_i^2) \cdot w \quad (2)$$

where: V – volume subjected to the stress field of a given distribution, r_o and r_i – outer and inner radius of the curved specimen, w – specimen width. As a result of the application of the above formula the stressed volumes of 157mm³, 1256mm³ and 10084mm³ were obtained for the 16-, 32-, and 64-ply specimen (C, D and F series) respectively. The ratio of the calculated volumes for the middle and small specimen, as well as for the large and middle specimen is 8, which corresponds to scaling principle described in the beginning of this paper. According to this principle each linear dimension is multiplied by a factor of 2, hence the volume is 2³ = 8. The stressed volume calculated by given formula includes the upper part of the curved section of the specimen, where the interlaminar stress is of positive sign (tensile). The detailed calculations of the stressed volumes for scaled specimen are given in Table below:

Table 6. Stressed volumes calculation for scaled specimen.

Specimen type (series)	Lay-up	Inner radius	Outer radius	Width	Volume
		r_i [mm]	r_o [mm]	w [mm]	V [mm ³]
C	(0 ₂ /±45 ₃) _S	4	6	5	157
D	(0 ₄ /±45 ₆) _S	8	12	10	1256
F	(0 ₈ /±45 ₁₂) _S	16	24	20	10048

The size effect for interlaminar tensile stresses at failure (strength) in the scaled specimens is presented in Figure 11. The following Figures 12 and 13 present the interlaminar shear stresses at failure. The least squares fitting lines of the Weibull model (Equation(1)) give straight lines also shown in the figures. The Weibull modulus m is calculated from a similar plots to those presented, where the slope of the fitting line is equal to -1/m.

The Weibull model fit for all interlaminar stress component data is satisfactory. The reduction of failure load while increasing the specimen size is the evidence of size effect. The smallest specimens were very difficult to manufacture and possibility of inaccuracies during lay-up was expected to be higher. This is associated with so-called manufacturing scale effect [5]. Also the spread of the measured failure load was higher than for larger specimens. This effect might also be the reason why the mean values of all stress components in the 32-ply specimen are above the fitting line. The calculated values of Weibull moduli for interlaminar stresses are presented in Table 7. The Weibull modulus for the interlaminar tensile strength σ_{zz} equals to 11,38, whereas for the interlaminar shear stresses equals to 6,05 for τ_{xz} and 5,95 for τ_{yz} . Those results show the strong evidence for the size effects in the free edge interlaminar stresses. Moreover, the size effects in interlaminar shear stresses at the free edge are higher than in case of interlaminar tensile stresses. The results show the evidence of size effects in curved composite laminates with failure controlled by free edge delamination.

Table 7. Weibull modulus m for interlaminar stresses in scaled specimen.

Weibull modulus	σ_{zz}	τ_{xz}	τ_{yz}
m	11,38	6,05	5,95

The Weibull moduli for in-plane stresses at failure in the same specimens were calculated for comparison. Detailed calculation is not presented here, however, the values were in the range of 8-9. This stays in a good agreement with the values of Weibull modulus for moment per unit width at failure of 8,53 reported elsewhere [5].

Figure 11. Size effect for interlaminar tensile stress σ_{zz} in curved beam bending.

Figure 12. Size effect for interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} in curved beam bending.

Figure 13. Size effect for interlaminar shear stress τ_{yz} in curved beam bending.

CONCLUSIONS

Presented results of the computer simulations of the interlaminar stress distributions in scaled specimen with free edge induced failure have shown the evidence for the size effects, known for other failure types [1, 2, 4]. The effect is particularly important for the interlaminar shear stresses, where there is a reduction in stress of up to 50% for an increase in the specimen linear dimensions by a factor of 4 (by factor of 16 for specimen volume), compared with 30% for interlaminar tensile stress.

The Weibull theory describes the size effects reasonably well giving the values of Weibull moduli of 11,38 for interlaminar tensile stress and around 6,0 for interlaminar shear stress (6,05 for τ_{xz} and 5,95 for τ_{yz}). The results are not consistent with the results obtained by Wisnom [4]. However, his analyses were conducted on unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy composites. No work on the size effects in the free edge failures were known to the author at the date of submitting this paper.

The care has to be taken when interpreting the presented results as the free edge stresses may cause the effects related to ply thickness. Those are difficult to distinguish from the effects of stressed volume. The way to separate those effects would be to perform similar analyses for the scaled specimen where ply thickness is scaled rather than the number of plies. Further work should also be performed to analyse the actual stressed volumes at the free edge.

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